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Protocol for a Systematic Mapping Study on
**Security in Telehealth Systems from a Software
Engineering Viewpoint**

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Introduction

Telehealth systems are telecommunication technology that support and promote long-distance clinical health care, patient and professional health-related education, public health and health administration. Telehealth has also made it easier for health care professionals in remote field settings to obtain guidance from professionals elsewhere in diagnosis, care and referral of patients.

According to InterimHealthcare¹, Telehealth is different from telemedicine because it refers to a broader scope of remote healthcare services than telemedicine. While telemedicine refers specifically to remote clinical services, telehealth can refer to remote non-clinical services, such as provider training, administrative meetings, and continuing medical education, in addition to clinical services.

Most telemonitoring systems wirelessly capture vital sign information and transmit the data to a center which has trained health care professionals. The system captures any or all vital signs depending on the individual's needs such as blood pressure & glucose levels, weight, SpO2 & temperature. The individual's caregiver, physician or family members can access the information remotely at any time, and are alerted when any levels are outside the individual's predetermined parameters and personal care plan. Telemonitoring systems are like having a doctor watching over the individual in the comfort of his or her own home.

Telehealth systems consist of software systems whose purpose is to provide specific functionalities (for example, software for remote patient monitoring) and incorporate emerging technologies to provide better remote services to their patients. This adoption brings various benefits to patient care, but also leads to new challenges, such as security. Telehealth usually involves bidirectional, digital collection and communication of sensitive health data among health care providers and patients, which increase potential risks and threats on privacy and security. Even though researchers have reported several security issues related to Telehealth systems, there is not a clear vision about which *type* of security issues Telehealth systems must face and which telehealth components and medical supplies are affected. Moreover, it is also not explicit which solutions have been proposed for these issues or if there are reuse of solutions for recurring security problems. Regarding software systems, there is also limited discussion about how to build secure Telehealth systems, which means ignoring the techniques and methods that are useful for this purpose.

In this systematic mapping study (SMS), we detect and characterize security issues in Telehealth systems. We selected 41 primary studies from over more than a thousand studies. We applied a rigorous protocol to extract, classify and organize relevant studies. Furthermore, we examined which areas of Software Engineering are essential to address security issues in the context of

¹ <https://www.interimhealthcare.com/education-center/home-care-technology/telehealth-systems/>

Telehealth. Also, we discussed the role of Software Engineering to address the potential challenges that we identify from primary studies.

Related work

Diverse contributions have been proposed related to security in Telehealth environments.

Garg et al.² conducted a systematic review concerning security in Telemedicine. The authors focused their study on physical security, and they discussed issues related to legalities, policies, and standards.

Zeadally et al.³ performed a literature review on security attacks on Electronic Health Systems (E-Health). The authors highlighted that telecommunications technology used by E-Health applications would face more sophisticated attacks. In the context of IoT and Cloud, Ida et al.⁴ also investigated security. The authors discussed the gap between IoT systems and vulnerabilities in the context of E-Health systems.

In the context of network communication, Kompara et al.⁵ conducted a survey on security in intra-body area network communication. The authors describe security issues that surround body sensor networks.

Despite the significant contribution of previous studies, our study differs from the previous ones in the discussion regarding security issues in Telehealth systems and Software Engineering. Previous studies focus on investigating security from a clinical and operational perspective but they do not discuss which aspects of Software Engineering are critical on secure Telehealth systems development.

² V. Garg, J. Brewer, Telemedicine security: a systematic review, *Journal of diabetes science and technology* 5 (3) (2011) 768{777.

³ S. Zeadally, J. T. Isaac, Z. Baig, Security attacks and solutions in electronic health (e-health) systems, *Journal of medical systems* 40 (12) (2016) 263.

⁴ I. B. Ida, A. Jemai, A. Loukil, A survey on security of iot in the context of ehealth and clouds, *Design Test Symposium (IDT)* (2016) 25{30.

⁵ M. Kompara, M. Holbl, Survey on security in intra-body area network communication, *Ad Hoc Networks* 70 (2018) 23{43.

Research process

In order to perform the SMS, we followed the guidelines proposed by Petersen et al.⁶ for conducting systematic mapping studies, and we complemented our mapping review process with the strategies presented by Kitchenham et al.⁷ for performing systematic literature reviews.

We also used the proposal of Watzlaf et al.⁸, which describes a protocol for systematic reviews of Telehealth privacy and security research, to complement our SMS. This protocol suggests methods and designs that help define more precisely the context of Telehealth systems. For example, the protocol suggests searching for specialized databases such as PubMed, EMBASE, INSPEC, among others.

Goal and research questions

The goal of this SMS is to detect, *organize and characterize security issues in Telehealth systems from a Software Engineering perspective*. Therefore, in order to achieve the aforementioned goal, we described the following research questions (RQ's).

- RQ1: *Which research themes are associated with security in Telehealth systems?* Rationale: By answering this RQ, we aim at detecting those research themes that characterize primary studies. For this reason, it is possible to identify the main security problems that health institutions must face when using Telehealth systems.
- RQ2: *Which security issues have been reported in Telehealth systems?* Rationale: This RQ investigates which type of security issues (such as attacks, vulnerabilities, threats, and others) Telehealth systems have been faced. Likewise, we show the main components of Telehealth systems as well as the medical supplies that are affected by security issues.
- RQ3: *Which solutions have been proposed for security issues in Telehealth systems?* Rationale: This RQ aims to identify and categorize proposals and the techniques or methods used to handle security issues. With this in mind, we organized security solutions based on security strategies.

⁶ K. Petersen, R. Feldt, S. Mujtaba, M. Mattsson, Systematic mapping studies in software engineering, International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering (EASE) 8 (68-77).

⁷ B. Kitchenham, S. Charters, Guidelines for performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering, Keele University and Durham University Joint ReportTech.rep.ebse 2007-001.

⁸ V. J. Watzlaf, D. R. Dealmeida, L. Zhou, L. M. Hartman, Protocol for a systematic review of telehealth privacy and security research to identify best practices, International journal of telerehabilitation 7 (2) (2015) 15.

Search and refinement

The goal of the search and refinement phases is to retrieve a comprehensive set of studies that are relevant and representative according to the main topic of this SMS. Therefore, prior to executing the selection criteria, we explored several databases in order to collect studies with different points of views (e.g., technical, medical, and others). To do this, we defined three phases, where the two first ones contain set of different electronic databases. In sections Phase I, Phase II, and Phase III , we further described each phase.

Search string

To define the search string, we used the P.I.C.O.C (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Context) framework⁹. This framework helps researchers to connect the different parts of the research question towards a meaningful and valid research string. Therefore, each element of the framework is broken down as follows:

- *Population*: Telehealth + Telemedicine + Telecare + systems
- *Intervention*: Approach and methodologies related to security in Telehealth systems
- *Comparison*: Not applicable
- *Outcome*: Classification template with primary studies
- *Context*: Academic peer-reviewed articles

We combined each element with logical ANDs and ORs. Therefore, we defined the following search string:

((telehealth OR tele health OR tele-health) OR (telemedicine OR tele medicine OR tele-medicine) OR (telecare OR tele care OR tele-care)) AND (system OR application OR software)
AND (security OR sec)

Phase I

As Kitchenham et al. suggest, in furtherance of gather as much information as possible, we selected seven databases commonly used in SMS in software engineering.

⁹ W. S. Richardson, M. C. Wilson, J. Nishikawa, R. S. Hayward, The well-built clinical question: a key to evidence-based decisions, ACP Journal Club 123 (3) A12{3.

Name	Link
IEEE Xplorer	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org
Springer Link	https://link.springer.com
ACM Library	https://dl.acm.org
Wiley	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com
Web of Science	http://login.webofknowledge.com
ScienceDirect	https://www.sciencedirect.com
Scopus	https://www.scopus.com/home.uri

Phase II

In this phase, we explored databases mentioned in health-related SMS. These studies contain not only technical aspects regarding health (in general) but also clinical ones. This gives the possibility of having a more comprehensive observation about the focus of this SMS.

Name	Link
PubMed	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/
EMBASE	https://www.embase.com/login
INSPEC	https://inspecdirect.theiet.org

Phase III

In this phase, we proceed to refine the selection of primary studies. For this, we applied selection criteria filters in order to, then, classify them. Subsequently, we analyzed the classified primary studies using a quality assessment. Finally, we proceed to extract the most relevant data.

Snowballing process

To identify more relevant studies, we also executed the snowballing procedure according to the guidelines proposed by Wholin et al¹⁰. The main goal of this process is to expand the set of potentially relevant studies by considering each study selected in the previous Phases I and II, and focusing on those articles, either citing and cited by it.

We performed both backward and forwarded snowballing (i.e., references, citations) procedures by taking nine selected studies as an initial data set. After this step, we obtained the final set of studies for data extraction to answer our RQs.

Selection criteria

From the set of studies obtained in Phase I and II, we defined the following inclusion and exclusion criteria in order to obtain primary studies.

- Inclusion criteria:
 - The study is related to Telehealth, Telemedicine or Telecare systems
 - The study should focus on security issues
 - The study should provide the solutions, techniques or methods used to handle security issues
 - The study should describe how security issues affect Healthcare organizations and their people (patients, practitioners, administrative staff, and others)
 - The study should be written in English
- Exclusion criteria:
 - Short studies (less than 3 pages)
 - Secondary or tertiary studies (such as literature reviews, surveys, and others)
 - Studies without full text available
 - Studies structured as tutorial, editorials, and others

¹⁰ C. Wohlin, Guidelines for snowballing in systematic literature studies and a replication in software engineering, Proceedings of the 18th international conference on evaluation and assessment in software engineering (2014) 38.

In this step, we invited healthcare professionals to review and discuss the selection criteria. The experience and clinical vision of these professionals help to be consistent and unbiased with the selection criteria. By using the feedback of them, we aim to ensure that the study selection results are objectives.

Classification

We classified primary studies based on the following classification scheme:

Research themes (RQ1)

In this RQ, we applied the approach proposed by Braun et al.¹¹ to identify main research themes concerning primary studies. Research themes are related to Thematic Analysis (TA), which is a method for systematically identifying, organizing, and offering insight into patterns of meaning (themes). Through focusing on purpose across a data set, TA allows the researcher(s) to see and make sense of collective or shared meanings and experiences. TA is composed by six steps, which are:

1. *Familiarizing with the data*: Transcribing data (if necessary), reading and re-reading the data, noting down initial ideas.
2. *Generating initial codes*: Coding interesting features of the data in a systematic fashion across the entire data set, collating data relevant to each code.
3. *Searching for themes*: Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each potential theme.
4. *Reviewing themes*: Checking in the themes work in relation to the coded extracts and the entire data set, generating a thematic "map" of the analysis.
5. *Defining and naming themes*: Ongoing analysis to refine the specifics of each theme, and the overall story the analysis tells; generating clear definitions and names for each theme.
6. *Producing the report*: The final opportunity for analysis. Selection of vivid, compelling extract examples, final analysis of selected extracts, relating back of the analysis to the research question and literature, producing a scholarly report of the analysis.

¹¹ V. Braun, V. Clarke, Using thematic analysis in psychology, *Qualitative research in psychology* 3 (2) (2006) 77-101.

Security issues (RQ2)

Inspired in databases like Common Vulnerabilities and Exposure (CVE), Common Weaknesses Enumeration (CWE), and others; we classified security issues in:

- *Attacks*: Information security incident that involves an attempt to obtain, alter, destroy, remove, implant or reveal information without authorized access or permission.
- *Vulnerabilities*: Cyber-security term that refers to a flaw in a system that can leave it open to attack.
- *Threats*: Anything that has the potential to cause serious harm to a computer system.
- *Weaknesses*: Flaws, faults, bugs, and other errors in software implementation, code, design, or architecture that if left unaddressed could result in systems and networks being vulnerable to attack.

Solutions (RQ3)

Regarding this RQ, we classified solutions based on *security strategies*. These strategies are inspired by the categories defined in the security tactics taxonomy proposed by Fernandez et al.¹², which are:

- *Detect attacks*: The solutions that are characterized by this strategy aim to identify potential attacks.
- *Stop or mitigate attacks*: This strategy intends to describe primary studies whose solutions aim to resist attacks.
- *React to attacks*: The objective of this strategy is to identify primary studies whose solutions attempt to respond to potential attacks.
- *Recover from attacks*: This strategy describes solutions that restore systems once it has detected and attempted to resist an attack.

Quality assessment

We established quality criteria in order to assess the primary studies' quality selected by the SMS. To achieve this task, we invited health professionals to set quality criteria. We decided to

¹² E. B. Fernandez, H. Astudillo, G. Pedraza-Garca, Revisting architectural tactics for security, European Conference on Software Architecture (2015) 55-69.

evaluate each quality criterion as Y (yes, *value=1*), P (partially, *value=0,5*), and N (no, *value=0*). After brainstorming sessions, we defined the following quality criteria:

- QC1: *Is there a clear description of the aims of the research?*
- QC2: *Does the study include research, practices or recommendations about security in Telehealth systems?*
- QC3: *Does the study explain how security issues affect Healthcare organizations?*
- QC4: *Does the study describe procedures, techniques or methods to handle security issues in Telehealth systems?*

Data extraction

In order to conduct a rigorous data extraction, the following table describes the data extraction scheme used in this SMS.

ID	Data item	Description	RQ
I1	Author(s)	The authors' full name	
I2	Title	The study's title	
I3	Year	Publication year	
I4	Venue	Name of the publishing venue	
I5	Publication type	Journal, conference, workshop, or book chapter	
I6	Validation type	Case study, empirical study, experiment, survey, empirical strategies comparison, replications, and others	
I7	Research classification	Classification criteria proposed by Wieringa et al.	
I8	Research themes	Thematic analysis proposed by Braun et al.	RQ1
I9	Security issues	Attacks, vulnerabilities, threats, and weaknesses	RQ2
I10	Solutions	Detect attacks, stop or mitigate attacks, react to attacks, or recover from attacks	RQ3

Data items I1 to I5 collect the primary data of each study. Regarding I6, this data item identifies the empirical strategies used by each primary study. We used the Wholin et al.¹³ empirical organization to perform the aforementioned empirical identification. I7 classify the research type of each study. For this, we used the proposal of Wieringa et al.¹⁴, which classify research type as follow:

- *Evaluation research*: These studies address the investigation of a problem in practice or implementation of a technique in practice.
- *Proposal of solution*: These articles propose a solution technique and argue for its relevance, without a full-blown validation.
- *Validation research*: These articles investigate the properties of a solution proposal that has not yet been implemented in practice.
- *Philosophical papers*: These articles sketch a new way of looking at things, a new conceptual framework, etc.
- *Opinion papers*: These articles contain the author's opinion about what is wrong or good about something, how we should do something, etc.
- *Personal experience papers*: In these articles, the emphasis is on what and not on why. The experience may concern one project or more, but it must be the author's personal experience.

Data analysis

The goal of this activity is to understand and to analyze security issues reported in Telehealth systems. Therefore, we used descriptive statistics, frequency analysis, and we tabulated the main results in order to obtain insight about primary studies. On the other hand, this analysis serves as a basis for discussing key findings among potential security challenges in Telehealth systems.

Dissemination

We plan to report our SMS to different audiences, to reach both researchers and practitioners. In the following list, we describe the steps we will engage:

¹³ C. Wohlin, P. Runeson, M. Hst, M. C. Ohlsson, B. Regnell, A. Wessln, Experimentation in software engineering, Springer Science Business Media.

¹⁴ R. Wieringa, N. Maiden, N. Mead, C. Rolland, Requirements engineering paper classification and evaluation criteria: a proposal and a discussion, Requirements Engineering 11 (1) (2006) 102-107.

- 1) We will report our main research-oriented findings and a detailed description of this study into a research publication in an international research conference
- 2) We will present all the details and raw data of the study
- 3) Depending on the obtained results, we will target a practitioners-oriented clinical magazine, to impact and enhance the current state of the practice about Telehealth security
- 4) We will use the SMS's results to research on healthcare organizations that use Telehealth systems